

Primitive Idempotents and Minimum Distance Bounds for Some Cyclic Codes of Length $8p^n$

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Abstract: Expression for primitive idempotents in semi-simple ring $R_{8p^n} \equiv \frac{GF(q)[x]}{\langle x^{8p^n}-1 \rangle}$, where p and q (of type $8k+3$ or $8k+7$) are distinct odd primes, n is a positive integer and order of q modulo $8p^n$ is $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$, are obtained. Generating polynomials and minimum distance bounds for the corresponding cyclic codes are also obtained.

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1 Introduction

Let $F(= GF(q))$ is a finite field of order q and G be a cyclic group of order n . For $n \geq 1$, the cyclic codes of length $8p^n$ over F can be viewed as ideals in the semi-simple ring $R_{8p^n} \equiv \frac{GF(q)[x]}{\langle x^{8p^n}-1 \rangle}$ [13]. The primitive idempotents of minimal cyclic codes of length m in case, when order of q modulo m is $\phi(m)$ for $m = 2, 4, p^n, 2p^n$ were computed in [8, 11]. The primitive idempotents of length p^n with order of q modulo p^n is $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$ were obtained in [12] and minimal quadratic residue codes of length p^n in [9]. Cyclic codes of length $2p^n$ over F , where order of q modulo $2p^n$ is $\frac{\phi(2p^n)}{2}$ were discussed in [10]. Minimal cyclic codes of length $p^n q$, where p and q are distinct odd primes were derived in [1, 3]. Further, when order of q modulo p^n is $\phi(p^n)$, the minimal cyclic codes of length $8p^n$ were discussed in [4, 5]. The minimal cyclic codes of length $8p^n$, where $q \equiv 1(\text{mod } 8)$ or $q \equiv 5(\text{mod } 8)$ and order of q modulo p^n is $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$ were obtained in [6, 7]. Irreducible cyclic codes of length $4p^n$ and $8p^n$, where $q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8)$ and $p/(q-1)$ were obtained in [2]. In present paper, we obtained cyclic codes of length $8p^n$ over F where q is of the form $8k+3$ or $8k+7$ and order of q modulo p^n is $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$. The q -cyclotomic cosets modulo $8p^n$ are obtained in section 2 and corresponding primitive idempotents in section 3. In section 4, we discussed generating polynomials and dimensions for the corresponding cyclic codes of length $8p^n$. The minimum distance or the bounds for minimum distance of these codes are obtained in section 5. At the end, an example is discussed to illustrate the various parameters for these codes.

2 Cyclotomic Cosets

Let $S = \{1, 2, \dots, 8p^n\}$. For $a, b \in S$, consider $a \sim b$ iff $a \equiv bq^i \pmod{8p^n}$ for some integer $i \geq 0$. This is an equivalence relation on S . The equivalence classes due to this relation are called q -cyclotomic cosets modulo $8p^n$. The q -cyclotomic coset containing $s \in S$ is $\Omega_s = \{s, sq, sq^2, \dots, sq^{t_s-1}\}$, where t_s is the smallest positive integer such that $sq^{t_s} \equiv s \pmod{8p^n}$.

Lemma 2.1. *[[10], Theorem 2.5] If $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$ is the order of q modulo p^n , then the order of q modulo p^{n-i} is $\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}$, $0 \leq i \leq n-1$.*

Lemma 2.2. *If $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$ is the order of q modulo p^n , then for $0 \leq i \leq n-1$, order of q modulo $2p^{n-i}$ is $\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}$.*

Proof. Since $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$ is the order of q modulo p^n , therefore by lemma 2.1, order of q modulo p^{n-i} is $\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}$, $1 \leq i \leq n-1$. Hence

$$q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^{n-i}} \quad (2.1)$$

Also, $q \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ so $q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. As $\gcd(2, p^{n-i}) = 1$, so $q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{2p^{n-i}}$, since order of q modulo p^{n-i} is $\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2} \Rightarrow \frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}$ is the smallest integer for which equation (2.1) holds. Hence order of q modulo $2p^{n-i}$ is $\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}$. \square

Lemma 2.3. *If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then order of q modulo $4p^{n-i}$ and $8p^{n-i}$ is also $\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}$ and for $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ order of q modulo $4p^{n-i}$ and $8p^{n-i}$ is $\phi(p^{n-i})$.*

Proof. Proof is on similar lines as that of lemma 2.2. \square

Lemma 2.4. *For $0 \leq i \leq n-1$ and $0 \leq k \leq \frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2} - 1$, $T \not\equiv q^k \pmod{8p^{n-i}}$, where $T = \lambda = (1 + 2p^n)$ or $T = \mu = 2(1 + 2p^n)$ or $T = \nu = (1 + 4p^n)$ or $T = \chi = (1 + 6p^n)$.*

Proof. Proof can be obtained by using lemmas 2.1 and 2.2. \square

Lemma 2.5. *Let p be an odd prime. Then there exists an integer g , $1 < g < 8p$ and is primitive root modulo p . Further when p is of the form $4k+1$ then order of g modulo 4 and modulo 8 is 2, and when p is of the form $4k+3$ then order of g modulo 4 is 1 and modulo 8 is 2. Also, if q is any prime power and $\text{g.c.d.}(q, p) = 1$, then $g \notin \{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p)}{2}-1}\}$.*

Proof. Consider the complete residue systems, $S_p = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$ modulo p , $S_2 = \{0, 1\}$ modulo 2, and $S_{2p} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2p-1\}$ modulo $2p$. Since $\text{g.c.d.}(2, p) = 1$, so there exist an integer $v \in S_p$ such that $2v - p = 1$. Let a be any primitive root mod p in S_p . For $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, let $g \equiv 2av + tp + 6ap \pmod{8p}$ where t is a prime of the form $8k_1 + 3$ implies $g \equiv a \pmod{p}$. Hence g is primitive root modulo p . Now, $g \equiv 2av + tp + 6ap \pmod{8}$ where t is a prime of the form $8k_1 + 3$, so $g \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ as p is of the form $4k+1$. Hence order of g modulo 4 and modulo 8 is 2. Now for $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, let $g \equiv 2av + tp + 4ap \pmod{8p}$ where t is a prime of the form $8k_2 + 7$ implies g is primitive root modulo p and order of g modulo 4 is 1 and modulo 8 is 2. Let $g \in \{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p)}{2}-1}\}$, so $g = q^i$ for some $1 \leq i \leq \frac{\phi(p)}{2} - 1$ equivalently $o(g) = o(q^i)$. As order of q modulo $8p$ is $\frac{\phi(p)}{2}$, so $o(q^i) \leq \frac{\phi(p)}{2}$ modulo $8p$. This implies $o(g) \leq \frac{\phi(p)}{2}$ modulo $8p$, but order of $g \pmod{8p}$ is $\phi(p)$, hence $g \notin \{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p)}{2}-1}\}$. \square

Lemma 2.6. *If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, there exist a fixed integer g satisfying $\gcd(g, 2pq) = 1$, $1 < g < 8p$, $g \not\equiv q^k \pmod{p}$ where $0 \leq k \leq \frac{\phi(p)}{2} - 1$, such that for $0 \leq j \leq n-1$, the set $\{1, q, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, g, gq, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}\}$ forms a reduced residue system modulo p^{n-j} and the set $\{1, q, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, g, gq, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \lambda, \lambda q, \lambda q^2, \dots, \lambda q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \lambda g, \lambda gq, \lambda gq^2, \dots, \lambda gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \nu, \nu q, \nu q^2, \dots, \nu q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \nu g, \nu gq, \dots, \nu gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \chi, \chi q, \dots,$*

$\chi q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \chi g, \chi gq, \dots, \chi gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}$ forms a reduced residue system modulo $8p^{n-j}$.

Proof. By lemma 2.1, order of q modulo p is $\frac{\phi(p)}{2}$, therefore $1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p)}{2}-1}$ are incongruent modulo p . As there are exactly $\phi(p)$ numbers in the reduced residue system modulo p . Therefore there exist a number g satisfying $\gcd(g, 2pq) = 1, 1 < g < 8p, g \not\equiv q^k \pmod{p}$ for $0 \leq k \leq \frac{\phi(p)}{2} - 1$. Then the set $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p)}{2}-1}, g, gq, gq^2, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p)}{2}-1}\}$ forms a reduced residue system modulo p . Since for $0 \leq k \leq \frac{\phi(p)}{2} - 1, g \not\equiv q^k \pmod{p}$. It follows that $g \not\equiv q^k \pmod{p^{n-j}}$ for $0 \leq k \leq \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} - 1$. Hence the set $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, g, gq, gq^2, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}\}$ forms a reduced residue system modulo p^{n-j} .

Similar result holds to show that the set $\{1, q, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, g, gq, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \lambda, \lambda q, \dots, \lambda q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \lambda g, \lambda gq, \dots, \lambda gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \nu, \nu q, \dots, \nu q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \nu g, \nu gq, \dots, \nu gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \chi, \chi q, \dots, \chi q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, \chi g, \chi gq, \chi gq^2, \dots, \chi gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}\}$ forms a reduced residue system modulo $8p^{n-j}$. □

Lemma 2.7. For $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, there exist a fixed integer g satisfying $\gcd(g, 2pq) = 1, 1 < g < 8p, g \not\equiv q^k \pmod{p}$ where $0 \leq k \leq \frac{\phi(p)}{2} - 1$, such that for $0 \leq j \leq n - 1$, the set $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}, g, gq, gq^2, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1}\}$ forms a reduced residue system modulo p^{n-j} and the set $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1}, g, gq, gq^2, \dots, gq^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1}, \nu, \nu q, \dots, \nu q^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1}, \nu g, \nu gq, \dots, \nu gq^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1}\}$ forms a reduced residue system modulo $8p^{n-j}$.

Proof. Proof is similar to that of lemma 2.5. □

Theorem 2.8. If $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then the $(16n + 5)$ q -cyclotomic cosets modulo $8p^n$ are given by

$\Omega_{ap^n} = \{ap^n\}$ and $\Omega_{bp^n} = \{bp^n, bp^nq\}$ where $a \in \mathbb{A} = \{0, 4\}$ and $b \in \mathbb{B}, \mathbb{B} = \{1, 2, 5\}$ for $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $\mathbb{B} = \{1, 2, 3\}$ for $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$ and for $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$,

$\Omega_{cp^i} = \{cp^i, cp^iq, cp^iq^2, \dots, cp^iq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}-1}\}$ where $c \in \mathbb{C} = \{1, 2, 4, 8, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \chi, g, 2g, 4g, 8g, \lambda g, \mu g, \nu g, \chi g\}$.

Proof. $\Omega_0 = \{0\}$ is trivial. Also $q^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, so $p^nq^2 \equiv p^n \pmod{8p^n}$ and hence $\Omega_{p^n} = \{p^n, p^nq\}$.

Similarly, $\Omega_{bp^n} = \{bp^n, bp^nq\}$.

As $q \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ this implies $4p^nq \equiv 4p^n \pmod{8p^n}$ and hence $\Omega_{4p^n} = \{4p^n\}$.

By lemma 2.3, $q^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{8p^{n-i}}$. Equivalently, $p^iq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}} \equiv p^i \pmod{8p^n}$.

Therefore, $\Omega_{p^i} = \{p^i, p^iq, p^iq^2, \dots, p^iq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}-1}\}$. Similarly, $\Omega_{cp^i} = \{cp^i, cp^iq, cp^iq^2, \dots, cp^iq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}-1}\}$.

Obviously, $|\Omega_0| = |\Omega_{4p^n}| = 1$. Also, $|\Omega_{p^n}| = |\Omega_{2p^n}| = |\Omega_{3p^n}| = |\Omega_{5p^n}| = 2$ and $|\Omega_{cp^i}| = \frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}$.

Therefore, $\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |\Omega_{p^i}| = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2} = \frac{\phi(p^n)}{2} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-1})}{2} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-2})}{2} + \dots + \frac{\phi(p)}{2} = \frac{p^n - 1}{2}$.

For $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$, $|\Omega_0| + |\Omega_{p^n}| + |\Omega_{2p^n}| + |\Omega_{4p^n}| + |\Omega_{5p^n}| + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \sum_c |\Omega_{cp^i}| = 8 + \frac{16(p^n-1)}{2} = 8p^n$.

For $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, $|\Omega_0| + |\Omega_{p^n}| + |\Omega_{2p^n}| + |\Omega_{3p^n}| + |\Omega_{4p^n}| + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \sum_c |\Omega_{cp^i}| = 8 + \frac{16(p^n-1)}{2} = 8p^n$. □

Theorem 2.9. If $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, then the $(10n + 5)$ q -cyclotomic cosets modulo $8p^n$ are given by

$\Omega_{ap^n} = \{ap^n\}, \Omega_{bp^n} = \{bp^n, bp^nq\}$ and for $0 \leq i \leq n - 1, \Omega_{dp^i} = \{dp^i, dp^iq, dp^iq^2, \dots, dp^iq^{\phi(p^{n-i})-1}\},$

$\Omega_{ep^i} = \{ep^i, ep^iq, ep^iq^2, \dots, ep^iq^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-i})}{2}-1}\},$ where $d \in \mathbb{D} = \{1, 2, \nu, g, 2g, \nu g\}$ and $e \in \mathbb{E} = \{4, 8, 4g, 8g\}$.

Proof. Proof is similar to that of theorem 2.8. □

3 Primitive Idempotents

Throughout this paper, we consider α as $8p^n$ th root of unity in some extension field of F . Let M_s be the minimal ideal in $R_{8p^n} = \frac{F[x]}{\langle x^{8p^n}-1 \rangle} \cong FC_{8p^n}$, generated by $\frac{(x^{8p^n}-1)}{m_s(x)}$, where $m_s(x)$ is the minimal polynomial for $\alpha^s, s \in \Omega_s$. We denote $P_s(x)$, the primitive idempotent in R_{8p^n} , corresponding to the minimal

ideal M_s , given by $P_s(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \sum_{t=0}^{8p^n-1} \rho_i^s x^t$ where $\rho_i^s = \sum_{s \in \Omega_s} \alpha^{-is}$ and $\bar{Z}_s = \sum_{s \in \Omega_s} x^s$.

Therefore,
$$P_s(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\sum_{a \in \mathbb{A}} \rho_{ap^n}^s \bar{Z}_{ap^n} + \sum_{b \in \mathbb{B}} \rho_{bp^n}^s \bar{Z}_{bp^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \sum_{c \in \mathbb{C}} \rho_{cp^i}^s \bar{Z}_{cp^i} \right] \text{ for } p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$$
 and
$$P_s(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\sum_{a \in \mathbb{A}} \rho_{ap^n}^s \bar{Z}_{ap^n} + \sum_{b \in \mathbb{B}} \rho_{bp^n}^s \bar{Z}_{bp^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left[\sum_{d \in \mathbb{D}} \rho_{dp^i}^s \bar{Z}_{dp^i} + \sum_{e \in \mathbb{E}} \rho_{ep^i}^s \bar{Z}_{ep^i} \right] \right] \text{ for } p \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \quad (3.1)$$

Lemma 3.1. For any odd prime p and a positive integer k , if β is primitive p^k th root of unity in some extension field of F , then

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(p^k)}{2}-1} (\beta^{q^t} + \beta^{gq^t}) = \begin{cases} -1, & k = 1 \\ 0, & k \geq 2 \end{cases}, \text{ when } q \text{ is quadratic residue modulo } p^k \text{ and}$$

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^k)-1} \beta^{q^t} = \begin{cases} -1, & k = 1 \\ 0, & k \geq 2 \end{cases}, \text{ when } q \text{ is primitive root modulo } p^k.$$

Proof. By lemma 2.6, the set $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^k)}{2}-1}, g, gq, gq^2, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^k)}{2}-1}\}$ is a reduced residue system

$(\text{mod } p^k)$. So,
$$\sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(p^k)}{2}-1} (\beta^{q^t} + \beta^{gq^t}) = \sum_{t=0}^{p^k-1} \beta^t - \sum_{t=1, p/t}^{p^k} \beta^t = - \sum_{t=1}^{p^k-1} \beta^{pt}.$$

If $k = 1$, then $-\beta^p = -1$. If $k \geq 2$, then $\beta^p \neq 1$, therefore,
$$\sum_{t=1}^{p^k-1} \beta^{pt} = \beta^p(1 + \beta^p + \dots + \beta^{p^{k-1}}) = \beta^p \frac{(\beta^{p^k} - 1)}{\beta^p - 1} = 0.$$
 For the remaining part see [[3], lemma 4]. □

Lemma 3.2. For $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$, $\lambda^2 \Omega_{p^i} = \nu^2 \Omega_{p^i} = \chi^2 \Omega_{p^i} = \Omega_{p^i} = \lambda \Omega_{\lambda p^i} = \nu \Omega_{\nu p^i} = \chi \Omega_{\chi p^i}$ and $\mu^2 \Omega_{p^i} = 4 \Omega_{p^i} = \mu \Omega_{\mu p^i} = 2 \Omega_{2p^i} = \Omega_{4p^i}$.

Proof. Since $\lambda^2, \nu^2, \chi^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{8p^n}$ and $\mu^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{8p^n}$ so, the required result holds. □

Lemma 3.3. For $\Omega_{p^n}, \Omega_{2p^n}, \Omega_{3p^n}, \Omega_{4p^n}$ and Ω_{5p^n}

$-\Omega_{p^n} = \Omega_{5p^n}, -\Omega_{2p^n} = \Omega_{2p^n}$ and $-\Omega_{4p^n} = \Omega_{4p^n}$ for $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$.

and $-\Omega_{p^n} = \Omega_{p^n}, -\Omega_{2p^n} = \Omega_{2p^n}, -\Omega_{3p^n} = \Omega_{3p^n}, -\Omega_{4p^n} = \Omega_{4p^n}$ for $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$.

Proof. We have $\Omega_{p^n} = \{p^n, p^n q\}$ and $\Omega_{5p^n} = \{5p^n, 5p^n q\}$. We claim that $-p^n \equiv 5p^n q \pmod{8p^n}$.

For this, we have $5p^n q + p^n = (5q+1)p^n = \{5(8k+3) + 1\}p^n = 40k + 16p^n \equiv 0 \pmod{8p^n}$ so, $-\Omega_{p^n} = \Omega_{5p^n}$.

Other equalities holds trivially. □

Lemma 3.4. (i). If $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$, then $-\Omega_1 = \Omega_\nu$ for $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $-\Omega_1 = \Omega_g$ for $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

(ii). If $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, then $-\Omega_1 = \Omega_1$ for $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $-\Omega_1 = -\Omega_{\nu g}$ for $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Proof. (i). Clearly, $\nu = 1 + 4p^n \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$ and $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$, so $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$.

Equivalently $\nu q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$. Now $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p^n}$ and $(1 + 4p^n) \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$,

so $\nu q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p^n}$. But $(8, p^n) = 1$ and $\nu q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv -1 \pmod{8p^n}$. Hence the result holds.

Since $g \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$ and for even k, $q^k \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, $gq^k \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$ and $\lambda \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$

Now $\lambda gq^k \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$ also $\lambda = 1 + 2p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$ and $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$.

As $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$ is odd so $q^k \not\equiv -1 \pmod{p^n}$ for any k. The set $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^n-j)}{2}-1}, g, gq, gq^2, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^n-j)}{2}-1}\}$

form a reduced residue system mod p^n , so $gq^k \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$ and $\lambda gq^k \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$.

But $(8, p^n) = 1$ so $\lambda gq^k \equiv -1 \pmod{8p^n}$. So the result holds.

(ii). Clearly, $\chi = 1 + 6p^n \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$ and $q \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$, so $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$.

Now $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p^n}$. But $(8, p^n) = 1$, therefore $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{4}} \equiv -1 \pmod{8p^n}$. Thus the result holds.

Since $g \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and for even k, $q^k \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, $gq^k \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $\nu \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$

Further, $\nu gq^k \equiv -1 \pmod{8}$ also $\nu = 1 + 4p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$ and $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$.
 And $q^k \not\equiv -1 \pmod{p^n}$ for any k. As the set $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\frac{\phi(p^n-j)}{2}-1}, g, gq, gq^2, \dots, gq^{\frac{\phi(p^n-j)}{2}-1}\}$ form a reduced residue system mod p^n , so $gq^k \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$ and $\nu gq^k \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$.

But $(8, p^n) = 1$, so $\nu gq^k \equiv -1 \pmod{8p^n}$. Hence $-\Omega_1 = \Omega_{\nu g}$. □

Notations: For $0 \leq j \leq n - 1$, define

$$A_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{gp^j}} \alpha^s, B_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda gp^j}} \alpha^s, C_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^s, D_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^s, E_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2gp^j}} \alpha^s,$$

$$F_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2p^j}} \alpha^s, G_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4gp^j}} \alpha^s, H_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^j}} \alpha^s, I_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8gp^j}} \alpha^s, J_j = p^j \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^s.$$

Here, $A_j^q = A_j$, so $A_j \in F$. Similarly $B_j, C_j, D_j, E_j, F_j, G_j, H_j, I_j$ and J_j all are in F .

The sets M_1, M_2 and M_3 are defined as follows

$M_1 = \{\mu\}$, $M_2 = \{\lambda, \chi\}$ and $M_3 = \{\lambda, \mu, \chi\}$ for $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $M_1 = M_2 = M_3 = \emptyset$, the empty set for $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.

Theorem 3.5. (i). For $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$, the expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to $\Omega_0, \Omega_{p^n}, \Omega_{2p^n}, \Omega_{4p^n}$ and Ω_{5p^n} are given by

$$P_0(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + \sum_{m \in M_3} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i})\}]$$

$$P_{p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{p^{2n}} + \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} + (\alpha^{p^{2n}} + \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{-(\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+i}}) \sum_{m \in M_2} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i})\}]$$

$$P_{2p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{4p^n} [\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{\bar{Z}_{2p^i} - \bar{Z}_{4p^i} - \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \sum_{m \in M_1} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i})\}]$$

$$P_{4p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} - \bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{-\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - \sum_{m \in M_3} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i})\}]$$

$$P_{5p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{p^{2n}} + \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} - (\alpha^{p^{2n}} + \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+i}}) \sum_{m \in M_2} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i})\}]$$

(ii). For $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, the expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to $\Omega_0, \Omega_{p^n}, \Omega_{2p^n}, \Omega_{3p^n}$ and Ω_{4p^n} are given by

$$P_0(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + \sum_{m \in M_3} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i})\}]$$

$$P_{p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{p^{2n}} - \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - (\alpha^{p^{2n}} - \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i}$$

$$+ 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} \\ + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+i}}) \sum_{m \in M_2} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i})\}]$$

$$P_{2p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{4p^n} [\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{ \bar{Z}_{2p^i} - \bar{Z}_{4p^i} - \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \sum_{m \in M_1} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i}) \}]$$

$$P_{3p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{p^{2n}} - \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} + (\alpha^{p^{2n}} - \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{ -(\alpha^{p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} \\ - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} \\ - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+i}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+i}}) \sum_{m \in M_2} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i}) \}]$$

$$P_{4p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} - \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{ -\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} \\ + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - \sum_{m \in M_2} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i}) \}]$$

Proof. (i). To evaluate $P_0(x)$, take $s = 0$ in (3.1), then $\rho_k^0 = \sum_{s \in \Omega_0} \alpha^0 = 1$ for all $0 \leq k \leq 8p^n - 1$.

$$\text{Therefore, } P_0(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{ \bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \\ + \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + \sum_{m \in M_3} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i}) \}]$$

For the evaluation of $P_p(x)$, take $s = p^n$ in $P_s(x)$, so we have to compute $\rho_k^{p^n}$ for $k = 0, p^n, 2p^n, 4p^n, 5p^n, p^i, 2p^i, 4p^i, 8p^i, \lambda p^i, \mu p^i, \nu p^i, \chi p^i, gp^i, 2gp^i, 4gp^i, 8gp^i, \lambda gp^i, \mu gp^i, \nu gp^i, \chi gp^i$.

$$\text{Here, } \rho_k^{p^n} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^n}} \alpha^{-ks} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{5p^n}} \alpha^{ks} = \alpha^{5p^{n-k}} + \alpha^{5p^{n+k}} = \alpha^{5p^{n-k}} + \alpha^{7p^{n-k}}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \rho_0^{p^n} = -\rho_{4p^n}^{p^n} = -\rho_{8p^i}^{p^n} = \rho_{8p^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{4gp^i}^{p^n} = \rho_{8gp^i}^{p^n} = 2. \\ \rho_{p^n}^{p^n} = -\rho_{5p^n}^{p^n} = -(\alpha^{p^{2n}} + \alpha^{3p^{2n}}), \rho_{2p^n}^{p^n} = \rho_{2p^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{\mu p^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{2gp^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{\mu gp^i}^{p^n} = 0. \\ \rho_{p^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{\nu p^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{gp^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{\nu gp^i}^{p^n} = -(\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}}). \\ \rho_{\lambda p^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{\chi p^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{\lambda gp^i}^{p^n} = -\rho_{\chi gp^i}^{p^n} = -(\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+i}}).$$

$$\text{Thus } P_p(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{p^{2n}} + \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} + (\alpha^{p^{2n}} + \alpha^{3p^{2n}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{ -(\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} \\ + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+i}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} \\ - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+i}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+i}}) \sum_{m \in M_2} (\bar{Z}_{mp^i} + \bar{Z}_{m gp^i}) \}]$$

Similarly, we can evaluate required expressions using lemma 3.3.

(ii). Proof holds similar to that of (i). □

Lemma 3.6. For $0 \leq i \leq n, 0 \leq j \leq n - 1$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$,

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = \begin{cases} -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i + j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} G_{i+j}, & \text{if } i + j \leq n - 1, g \neq 1, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} H_{i+j}, & \text{if } i + j \leq n - 1, g = 1, \end{cases} \\ \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{8gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{8gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{8gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{8gp^i s} = \begin{cases} \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i + j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} I_{i+j}, & \text{if } i + j \leq n - 1, g \neq 1, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} J_{i+j}, & \text{if } i + j \leq n - 1, g = 1. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let $\delta = \alpha^{4p^{i+j}}$. Then, $\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = \sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1} \alpha^{4gp^{i+j} q^t} = \sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1} \delta^{gq^t}$.

If $i + j \geq n$, then $\delta^g = -1$. Therefore, $\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}$.

If $i + j \leq n - 1$, then δ is primitive $2p^{n-i-j}$ th root of unity.

And $\delta^{gq^l} \equiv \delta^{gq^r}$ if and only if $l \cong r \pmod{\frac{\phi(2p^{n-i-j})}{2}}$.

Hence, $\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = \sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1} \alpha^{4gp^{i+j} q^t} = \sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}-1} \delta^{gq^t} = \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{\phi(2p^{n-i-j})} \sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(2p^{n-i-j})}{2}-1} \delta^{gq^t}$
 $= \frac{p^{i+j}}{p^j} \sum_{t=0}^{\frac{\phi(2p^{n-i-j})}{2}-1} \delta^{gq^t} = \frac{1}{p^j} G_{i+j}$. Similarly, $\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = \frac{1}{p^j} H_{i+j}$.

Similar the result holds for other expression using lemma 3.1. □

Lemma 3.7. For $0 \leq i \leq n$, $0 \leq j \leq n - 1$ and $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{gp^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{4gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu gp^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = \begin{cases} -\phi(p^{n-j}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{2}{p^j} G_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g \neq 1, \\ \frac{2}{p^j} H_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g = 1, \end{cases} \\ \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4gp^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^j}} \alpha^{gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^j}} \alpha^{\nu gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4gp^j}} \alpha^{\nu p^i s} = \begin{cases} -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} G_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g \neq 1, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} H_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g = 1, \end{cases} \\ \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{8gp^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{gp^j}} \alpha^{8p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{8gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu gp^j}} \alpha^{8p^i s} = \begin{cases} \phi(p^{n-j}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{2}{p^j} I_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g \neq 1, \\ \frac{2}{p^j} J_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g = 1, \end{cases} \\ \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{gp^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\nu gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8gp^j}} \alpha^{\nu p^i s} = \begin{cases} \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} I_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g \neq 1, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} J_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g = 1. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proof of these equalities are same as lemma 3.6 using lemmas 3.1 and 3.2. □

Theorem 3.8. (i). The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{4p^j} and Ω_{8p^j} for $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} P_{4p^j}(x) &= \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{ \bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} - \bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ -\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} \right. \\ &+ \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{p^i} \\ &+ J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} \\ &+ I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} \} \\ P_{8p^j}(x) &= \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{ \bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \bar{Z}_{5p^n} \} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} \right. \\ &+ \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{p^i} \\ &+ J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\}$$

where $G_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1})$, $H_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1})$, $I_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1})$ and $J_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1})$ and for all $j \leq n - 2$, $G_j = H_j = I_j = J_j = 0$.

(ii). The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{4p^j} and Ω_{8p^j} for $q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8)$ and $p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$ are given by

$$P_{4p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} - \bar{Z}_{5p^n}\} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{-\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} \right]$$

$$P_{8p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} + \bar{Z}_{5p^n}\} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} \right]$$

where $G_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1})$, $H_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1})$, $I_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1})$ and $J_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1})$ and for all $j \leq n - 2$, $G_j = H_j = I_j = J_j = 0$.

(iii). The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{4p^j} and Ω_{8p^j} for $q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8)$ and $p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$ are given by

$$P_{4p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} - \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{-\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} \right]$$

$$P_{8p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} \right]$$

where $G_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1})$, $H_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1})$, $I_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1})$ and $J_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1})$ and for all $j \leq n - 2$, $G_j = H_j = I_j = J_j = 0$.

(iv). The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{4p^j} and Ω_{8p^j} for $q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8)$ and $p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$ are given by

$$P_{4p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} - \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{-\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} \right]$$

$$P_{8p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{ \bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{3p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} \} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \right. \\ \left. + \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{p^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \right. \\ \left. + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} \} \right] \\ \text{where } G_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1}), H_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1}), I_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1}) \text{ and} \\ J_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1}) \text{ and for all } j \leq n-2, G_j = H_j = I_j = J_j = 0.$$

Proof. (i) To evaluate $P_{4p^j}(x)$, take $s = 4p^j$ in (3.1) so we have to compute $\rho_k^{4p^j}$ for $k = 0, p^n, 2p^n, 4p^n, 5p^n, p^i, 2p^i, 4p^i, 8p^i, \lambda p^i, \mu p^i, \nu p^i, \chi p^i, gp^i, 2gp^i, 4gp^i, 8gp^i, \lambda gp^i, \mu gp^i, \nu gp^i, \chi gp^i$.

Since in this case $\Omega_{4p^j} = -\Omega_{4p^j}$, using lemma 3.4. So, $\rho_k^{4p^j} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^j}} \alpha^{-sk} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4ks}$.

Therefore, using lemma 3.6, we have

$$\rho_0^{4p^j} = -\rho_{p^n}^{4p^j} = \rho_{2p^n}^{4p^j} = \rho_{4p^n}^{4p^j} = -\rho_{5p^n}^{4p^j} = \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, \\ \rho_{p^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\lambda p^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\nu p^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\chi p^i}^{4p^j} = \begin{cases} -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} H_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, \end{cases} \\ \rho_{2p^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{4p^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{8p^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\mu p^i}^{4p^j} = \begin{cases} \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} J_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, \end{cases} \\ \rho_{gp^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\lambda gp^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\nu gp^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\chi gp^i}^{4p^j} = \begin{cases} -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} G_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, \end{cases} \\ \rho_{2gp^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{4gp^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{8gp^i}^{4p^j} = \rho_{\mu gp^i}^{4p^j} = \begin{cases} \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}, & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} I_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, \end{cases}$$

Therefore,

$$P_{4p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{ \bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{p^n} + \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} - \bar{Z}_{5p^n} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ -\bar{Z}_{p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} \right. \\ \left. + \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{p^i} \right. \\ \left. + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} \right. \\ \left. + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} \right]$$

Similarly, using lemma 3.4, 3.6 and 3.7, we can evaluate expressions for $P_{8p^j}(x)$ and other parts. □

We can obtain the expressions for $P_{4gp^j}(x), P_{8gp^j}(x)$ by interchanging G and I by H and J respectively in the expressions of $P_{4p^j}(x), P_{8p^j}(x)$ in same cases.

Lemma 3.9. For $0 \leq i \leq n$ and $0 \leq j \leq n-1$,

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{2gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{2gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\mu gp^i s} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } i+j \geq n, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} E_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g \neq 1, \\ \frac{1}{p^j} F_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1, g = 1. \end{cases}$$

Proof. proof can be obtained on similar lines as that of lemma 3.6 using lemmas 3.2 and 3.4. □

Theorem 3.10. (i) The expression for primitive idempotent corresponding to Ω_{2p^j} for $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ is given by

$$P_{2p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{ \bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} \} - \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \bar{Z}_{2p^i} - \bar{Z}_{4p^i} - \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} - \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} \right.$$

$$+ \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ F_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + F_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - E_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - E_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \}$$

where $E_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{2p^{2n-1} - p^{2(n-1)}} + p^{n-1})$, $F_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{2p^{2n-1} - p^{2(n-1)}} - p^{n-1})$ and for all $j \leq n-2$, $E_j = F_j = 0$.

(ii) The expression for primitive idempotent corresponding to Ω_{2p^j} for $p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$ is given by

$$P_{2p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_{2p^n} + \bar{Z}_{4p^n} \} + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ -\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + \bar{Z}_{8p^i} - \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ E_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{p^i} + 2G_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2p^i} + 2I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2I_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8p^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + F_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{gp^i} + 2H_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + 2J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2J_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + F_{i+j} \bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} \}]$$

where $E_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-\frac{1}{2}p^{2(n-1)} - \frac{3}{2}p^{2n-1}} + p^{n-1})$, $F_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{-\frac{1}{2}p^{2(n-1)} - \frac{3}{2}p^{2n-1}} - p^{n-1})$ and for all $j \leq n-2$, $E_j = F_j = 0$.

Proof. Proof can be obtained on similar lines as that of theorem 3.8 using lemmas 3.2, 3.4 and 3.9. \square

We can obtain the expression for $P_{2gp^j}(x)$ by interchanging E, G and H by F, H and I respectively in the expression of $P_{2p^j}(x)$ for same cases. Also we can obtain the expressions for $P_{\mu p^j}(x)$ by interchanging E, F, G and I by $-E, -F, H$ and J respectively and $P_{\nu p^j}(x)$ by interchanging E, G and I by $-F, H$ and J respectively in case $p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4)$.

Lemma 3.11. For $0 \leq i \leq n, 0 \leq j \leq n-1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{gp^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{\nu gp^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{\chi gp^i s} \\ &= \begin{cases} -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4), \\ -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{1}{p^j} A_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1. \end{cases} \\ \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda gp^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{\nu gp^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{gp^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\nu gp^i s} \\ &= \begin{cases} -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ -\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{1}{p^j} B_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1. \end{cases} \\ \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{\nu p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{\chi p^i s} \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2}(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{1}{p^j} C_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1. \end{cases} \\ \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda p^i s} &= \begin{cases} \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4}(\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}}), & \text{if } i+j \geq n, q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8) \text{ and } p \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4), \\ \frac{1}{p^j} D_{i+j}, & \text{if } i+j \leq n-1. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained on similar lines as that of lemma 3.6 using lemmas 3.2 and 3.4. □

Theorem 3.12. (i) The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{pj} , $\Omega_{\lambda pj}$, $\Omega_{\nu pj}$ and $\Omega_{\chi pj}$ for $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ are given by

$$P_{pj}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{ 2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{C}_{5p^n} \} \right. \\ + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ -(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \\ + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \\ \left. - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ -C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} \right. \\ \left. - D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \right. \\ \left. - E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} \right]$$

$$P_{\lambda pj}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{ 2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n} \} \right. \\ + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ -(\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \\ + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \\ \left. - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ -D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} \right. \\ \left. - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \right. \\ \left. + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} \right]$$

$$P_{\nu pj}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{ 2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n} \} \right. \\ + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \\ - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \\ + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} \\ + D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \\ \left. - E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} \right]$$

$$P_{\chi pj}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{ 2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n} \} \right. \\ + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \\ - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \\ + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} \\ + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} \\ \left. + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i} \} \right]$$

where A_{n-1} , B_{n-1} , C_{n-1} and D_{n-1} are calculated by the following relations

$$A_{n-1}^2 + B_{n-1}^2 + C_{n-1}^2 + D_{n-1}^2 = -\frac{3p^{2(n-1)}}{2} - \frac{p^{2(n-1)}}{2} - p^n + p^{n-1} \\ A_{n-1}C_{n-1} + B_{n-1}D_{n-1} = \frac{p^n}{2} - \frac{p^{(n-1)}}{2} + \frac{3p^{2(n-1)}}{4} - \frac{3p^{(2n-1)}}{4}$$

$$A_{n-1}B_{n-1} + C_{n-1}D_{n-1} = \frac{p^{(2n-1)}}{4} - \frac{p^{2(n-1)}}{4} - \frac{p^n}{2} + \frac{p^{(n-1)}}{2}$$

$$A_{n-1}D_{n-1} + B_{n-1}C_{n-1} = \frac{p^n}{2} - \frac{p^{(n-1)}}{2} + \frac{3p^{2(n-1)}}{4} - \frac{3p^{(2n-1)}}{4}$$

and for all $j \leq n - 2$, $A_j = B_j = C_j = D_j = 0$.

(ii) The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{p^j} , $\Omega_{\lambda p^j}$, $\Omega_{\nu p^j}$ and $\Omega_{\chi p^j}$ for $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ are given by

$$P_{p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} \right.$$

$$+ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{C}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i}$$

$$- (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i}$$

$$+ (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i}$$

$$+ D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i}$$

$$- E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\}$$

$$P_{\lambda p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} \right.$$

$$+ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i}$$

$$- (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i}$$

$$+ (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i}$$

$$+ J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i}$$

$$+ I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\}$$

$$P_{\nu p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} \right.$$

$$+ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{-(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i}$$

$$+ (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i}$$

$$- (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{-C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i}$$

$$- D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i}$$

$$- E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\}$$

$$P_{\chi p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \{2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} \right.$$

$$+ \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{4} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{-(\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i}$$

$$+ (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} + (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i}$$

$$- (\alpha^{\lambda p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3\lambda p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{-D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} - F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i}$$

$$- C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda p^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu p^i} + D_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi p^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\lambda gp^i}$$

$$+ E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\mu gp^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\chi gp^i}\}$$

where A_{n-1} , B_{n-1} , C_{n-1} and D_{n-1} are calculated by the following relations

$$A_{n-1}^2 + B_{n-1}^2 + C_{n-1}^2 + D_{n-1}^2 = \frac{3p^{2(n-1)}}{2} + \frac{p^{2(n-1)}}{2} + p^n - p^{n-1}$$

$$A_{n-1}C_{n-1} + B_{n-1}D_{n-1} = -\frac{p^n}{2} + \frac{p^{(n-1)}}{2} - \frac{3p^{2(n-1)}}{4} + \frac{3p^{(2n-1)}}{4}$$

$$A_{n-1}B_{n-1} + C_{n-1}D_{n-1} = \frac{p^{(2n-1)}}{4} - \frac{p^{2(n-1)}}{4} - \frac{p^n}{2} + \frac{p^{(n-1)}}{2}$$

$$A_{n-1}D_{n-1} + B_{n-1}C_{n-1} = \frac{p^n}{2} - \frac{p^{(n-1)}}{2} - \frac{3p^{2(n-1)}}{2} + \frac{3p^{(2n-1)}}{2}$$

and for all $j \leq n - 2$, $A_j = B_j = C_j = D_j = 0$.

(iii) The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{p^j} and $\Omega_{\nu p^j}$ for $q \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8)$ and $p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$ are given by

$$P_{p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n}\} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} \right. \\ \left. - 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + 2G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \right. \\ \left. + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + 2H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} \right]$$

$$P_{\nu p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n} - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{5p^n}\} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} \right. \\ \left. + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} + \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{-A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + 2G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \right. \\ \left. - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + 2H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} \right].$$

(iv) The expressions for primitive idempotents corresponding to Ω_{p^j} and $\Omega_{\nu p^j}$ for $q \equiv 7(\text{mod } 8)$ and $p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4)$ are given by

$$P_{p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{2\bar{Z}_0 + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} \right. \\ \left. + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{-A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + 2G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \right. \\ \left. - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + 2H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} \right]$$

$$P_{\nu p^j}(x) = \frac{1}{8p^n} \left[\frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \{2\bar{Z}_0 - (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^n} + (\alpha^{p^{n+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{n+j}})\bar{Z}_{3p^n} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^n}\} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\phi(p^{n-j})}{2} \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{(\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{p^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{Z}_{8p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} + (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{gp^i} - 2\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} \right. \\ \left. + 2\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - (\alpha^{p^{i+j}} - \alpha^{3p^{i+j}})\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{p^i} + E_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2p^i} + 2G_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4p^i} + 2I_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8p^i} - A_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu p^i} \right. \\ \left. + C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{gp^i} + F_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{2gp^i} + 2H_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{4gp^i} + 2J_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{8gp^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{Z}_{\nu gp^i}\} \right]$$

where $A_{n-1} = \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{\frac{47}{8}p^{2n-1} + \frac{47}{8}p^{2(n-1)} + 4p^n - 4p^{n-1}})$,

$C_{n-1} = -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{\frac{47}{8}p^{2n-1} + \frac{47}{8}p^{2(n-1)} + 4p^n - 4p^{n-1}})$ and for all $j \leq n - 2$, $A_j = C_j = 0$.

Proof. Proof can be obtained on similar lines as that of theorem 3.8 using lemmas 3.2, 3.4 and 3.11. \square

We can obtain the expressions for $P_{\nu gp^j}(x)$, $P_{\chi gp^j}(x)$, $P_{gp^j}(x)$ and $P_{\lambda gp^j}(x)$ by interchanging A, B, E, G and I by $-C, -D, F, H$ and J respectively in the expressions for $P_{p^j}(x)$, $P_{\lambda p^j}(x)$, $P_{\nu p^j}(x)$ and $P_{\chi p^j}(x)$

for same cases.

4 Dimension and Generating Polynomials

If α is primitive $8p^n$ th root of unity in some extension field of F , then $m_s(x) = \prod_{s \in \Omega_s} (x - \alpha^s)$ denote the minimal polynomial for α^s . Then the generating polynomial for cyclic code M_s of length $8p^n$ corresponding to the cyclotomic coset Ω_s is $\frac{x^{8p^n} - 1}{m_s(x)}$ and the dimension of minimal cyclic code M_s is equal to the cardinality of the class Ω_s [5].

Theorem 4.1. *The generating polynomial for the codes M_0, M_{2p^n} and M_{4p^n} are $(1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{8p^n - 1})$, $(x^6 - x^4 + x^2 - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$ and $(x^7 - x^6 + x^5 - x^4 + x^3 - x^2 + x - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$ respectively and the generating polynomial for $M_{p^n} \oplus M_{5p^n}$ is $(x^4 - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$ in case $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$ and it is also generating polynomial for $M_{p^n} \oplus M_{3p^n}$ in case $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$. Also, the generating polynomial for $M_{4p^i} \oplus M_{4gp^i}$ and $M_{8p^i} \oplus M_{8gp^i}$ are $(x^{p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} - 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$ and $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} - 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$ respectively.*

Proof. The minimal polynomial for α^0, α^{2p^n} and α^{4p^n} are $(x - 1)$, $(x^2 + 1)$ and $(x + 1)$ respectively. The corresponding generating polynomials are $(1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{8p^n - 1})$, $(x^6 - x^4 + x^2 - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$ and $(x^7 - x^6 + x^5 - x^4 + x^3 - x^2 + x - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$. The product of minimal polynomials satisfied by α^{p^n} and α^{5p^n} is $(x^4 + 1)$, so the generating polynomial for $M_{p^n} \oplus M_{5p^n}$ is $(x^4 - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$. Also, the product of minimal polynomial satisfied by α^{4p^i} and α^{4gp^i} is $\frac{x^{p^{n-i}} + 1}{x^{p^{n-i}-1} + 1}$. Therefore, the generating polynomial for $M_{4p^i} \oplus M_{4gp^i}$ is $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} - 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$. The product of minimal polynomial satisfied by α^{8p^i} and α^{8gp^i} is $\frac{x^{p^{n-i}} - 1}{x^{p^{n-i}-1} - 1}$. Therefore, the generating polynomial for $M_{8p^i} \oplus M_{8gp^i}$ is $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} - 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$. \square

Theorem 4.2. *For $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, the generating polynomial for the codes $M_{p^i} \oplus M_{2p^i} \oplus M_{\lambda p^i} \oplus M_{\mu p^i} \oplus M_{\nu p^i} \oplus M_{\chi p^i} \oplus M_{gp^i} \oplus M_{2gp^i} \oplus M_{\lambda gp^i} \oplus M_{\mu gp^i} \oplus M_{\nu gp^i} \oplus M_{\chi gp^i}$ is $(x^{2p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} - 1)(x^{4p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$ and for $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, the generating polynomial for $M_{p^i} \oplus M_{2p^i} \oplus M_{\nu p^i} \oplus M_{gp^i} \oplus M_{2gp^i} \oplus M_{\nu gp^i}$ is $(x^{2p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} - 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$.*

Proof. Proof follows similar to that of theorem 4.1. \square

5 Minimum Distance

Lemma 5.1. *If l is a cyclic code of length m generated by $g(x)$ and its minimum distance is d , then the code \bar{l} of length mk generated by $g(x)(1 + x^m + x^{2m} + \dots + x^{(k-1)m})$ is a repetition code of l repeated k times and its minimum distance is dk [3].*

Here, we find the minimum distance of the minimal cyclic code M_s of length $8p^n$, generated by the primitive idempotent P_s .

Theorem 5.2. *The minimum distance of the codes M_0, M_{2p^n} and M_{4p^n} are $8p^n, 4p^n$ and $8p^n$ respectively and for $q \equiv 3 \pmod{8}$, the codes M_{p^n} and M_{5p^n} are of minimum distance greater than or equal to $2p^n$. Also, for $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, the minimum distance of the codes M_{p^n} and M_{3p^n} are greater than or equal to $2p^n$.*

Proof. Since the generating polynomial for the code M_0 is $(1 + x + x^2 + \dots + x^{8p^n - 1})$, which is itself a polynomial of length $8p^n$, hence its minimum distance is $8p^n$. Also, the generating polynomial for the cyclic code M_{2p^n} is $(x^6 - x^4 + x^2 - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$. If we take a cyclic code of length 8 generated by the polynomial $(x^6 - x^4 + x^2 - 1)$, then the minimum distance of this code is 4, repeated p^n times. Also we can observe in similar way that the minimum distance of the cyclic code M_{4p^n} is $8p^n$.

Since the generating polynomial for the cyclic code $M(p^n, 5p^n)$ is $(x^4 - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$ therefore, if we take a code C of length 8 generated by the polynomial $(x^4 - 1)$, then the minimum distance of this code is 2. Since the cyclic code $M(p^n, 5p^n)$ generated by the polynomial $(x^4 - 1)(1 + x^8 + \dots + x^{8(p^n - 1)})$ is a repetition code of the code C , repeated p^n times. Hence its minimum distance is $2p^n$.

The codes corresponding to Ω_{p^n} and Ω_{5p^n} are subcodes of the above codes so, by [3, 5.4], their minimum distance is greater than or equal to $2p^n$. Similarly, for $q \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, the minimum distance of the codes Ω_{p^n} and Ω_{3p^n} is greater than or equal to $2p^n$. \square

Theorem 5.3. For $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$ and $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, the minimum distance of the cyclic codes $M_{4p^i}, M_{4gp^i}, M_{8p^i}$ and M_{8gp^i} are greater than or equal to $16p^i$ and for the codes $M_{p^i}, M_{gp^i}, M_{2p^i}, M_{2gp^i}, M_{\lambda p^i}, M_{\lambda gp^i}, M_{\mu p^i}, M_{\mu gp^i}, M_{\nu p^i}, M_{\nu gp^i}, M_{\chi p^i}$ and $M_{\chi gp^i}$ are greater than or equal to $8p^i$.

Proof. Consider the cyclic codes M_{4p^i} and M_{4gp^i} , since the generating polynomial of the cyclic code of length $8p^n$ is $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} - 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$, therefore, if we take a cyclic code C of length p^{n-i} generated by the polynomial $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} + 1)$, then the minimum distance of this code is 2. Now consider the cyclic code C_1 of length $2p^{n-i}$ generated by the polynomial $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} - 1)$ and so minimum distance of this code is 4, as it is 2 time repetition of the code C . Further, the minimum distance of the code C_2 of length $4p^{n-i}$ generated by the polynomial $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} - 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)$ is 8, as it is 2 time repetition of the code C_1 . Hence the minimum distance of the code C_3 of length $8p^{n-i}$ generated by the polynomial $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} - 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)$ and so minimum distance of this code is 16. Since the cyclic code of length $8p^n$ generated by the polynomial $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} - 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$ is a repetition code of the code C_3 , repeated p^i times. Hence its minimum distance is $16p^i$. The codes corresponding to M_{4p^i} and M_{4gp^i} are the sub codes of the above codes, so their minimum distances are greater than or equal to $16p^i$. Similarly, the minimum distance of the cyclic code M_{8p^i} and M_{8gp^i} of length $8p^n$ with generating polynomial $(x^{p^{n-i-1}} - 1)(x^{p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i}} + 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$ is also greater than or equal to $16p^i$.

Now, the product of generating polynomial for the cyclic codes $M_{p^i}, M_{gp^i}, M_{2p^i}, M_{2gp^i}, M_{\lambda p^i}, M_{\lambda gp^i}, M_{\mu p^i}, M_{\mu gp^i}, M_{\nu p^i}, M_{\nu gp^i}, M_{\chi p^i}$ and $M_{\chi gp^i}$ is $(x^{2p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} - 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$, therefore, if we take a code C of length $8p^{n-i}$ generated by the polynomial $(x^{2p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} - 1)$, then the minimum distance of this code is 8. Since the cyclic code C_1 of length $8p^n$ generated by the polynomial $(x^{2p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{4p^{n-i-1}} + 1)(x^{2p^{n-i}} - 1)(1 + x^{8p^{n-i}} + \dots + x^{8p^{n-i}(p^i - 1)})$ is a repetition code of the code C , repeated p^i times. Hence its minimum distance is $8p^i$.

The codes corresponding to $\Omega_{p^i}, \Omega_{gp^i}, \Omega_{2p^i}, \Omega_{2gp^i}, \Omega_{\lambda p^i}, \Omega_{\lambda gp^i}, \Omega_{\mu p^i}, \Omega_{\mu gp^i}, \Omega_{\nu p^i}, \Omega_{\nu gp^i}, \Omega_{\chi p^i}$ and $\Omega_{\chi gp^i}$ are the subcodes of above codes so, their minimum distances are greater than or equal to $8p^i$. \square

Theorem 5.4. For $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$ and $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, the minimum distance of the cyclic codes $M_{4p^i}, M_{4gp^i}, M_{8p^i}$ and M_{8gp^i} are greater than or equal to $16p^i$ and for the codes $M_{p^i}, M_{gp^i}, M_{2p^i}, M_{2gp^i}, M_{\nu p^i}$ and $M_{\nu gp^i}$ are greater than or equal to $8p^i$.

Proof. Proof is on similar lines as that of theorem 5.3. □

6 Example

Cyclic codes of length 24.

For $p = 3$, $n = 1$, $q = 7$, the q -cyclotomic cosets are

$$\Omega_0 = \{0\}, \Omega_1 = \{1, 7\}, \Omega_2 = \{2, 14\}, \Omega_3 = \{3, 21\}, \Omega_4 = \{4\}, \Omega_5 = \{5, 11\}, \Omega_6 = \{6, 18\}, \Omega_8 = \{8\}, \\ \Omega_9 = \{9, 15\}, \Omega_{10} = \{10, 22\}, \Omega_{12} = \{12\}, \Omega_{13} = \{13, 19\}, \Omega_{16} = \{16\}, \Omega_{17} = \{17, 23\}, \Omega_{20} = \{20\}$$

Also, $A_0 = 0$, $C_0 = 0$, $E_0 = 2$, $F_0 = 6$, $G_0 = 5$, $H_0 = 3$, $I_0 = 4$, $J_0 = 2$.

and the corresponding primitive idempotents in $\frac{GF(7)[x]}{\langle x^{24}-1 \rangle}$ are

$$P_0(x) = \frac{1}{24}[\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_3 + \bar{Z}_6 + \bar{Z}_9 + \bar{Z}_{12} + \bar{Z}_{15} + \bar{Z}_{18} + \bar{Z}_{21} + \bar{Z}_4 + \bar{Z}_8 + \bar{Z}_{13} + \bar{Z}_{17} + \bar{Z}_5 + \bar{Z}_{10} + \bar{Z}_{20} + \bar{Z}_{16} + \bar{Z}_{17}]$$

$$P_1(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_{12} + 2\bar{Z}_2 + 10\bar{Z}_4 + 8\bar{Z}_8 + 6\bar{Z}_{10} + 6\bar{Z}_{20} + 4\bar{Z}_{16}]$$

$$P_2(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_6 + 2\bar{Z}_{12} + 2\bar{Z}_1 + 10\bar{Z}_2 + 8\bar{Z}_4 + 8\bar{Z}_8 + 2\bar{Z}_{13} + 6\bar{Z}_5 + 6\bar{Z}_{10} + 4\bar{Z}_{20} + 4\bar{Z}_{16} + 6\bar{Z}_{17}]$$

$$P_3(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_{12} - 2\bar{Z}_4 + 2\bar{Z}_8 - 2\bar{Z}_{20} + 2\bar{Z}_{16}]$$

$$P_4(x) = \frac{1}{24}[\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_3 + \bar{Z}_6 - \bar{Z}_9 + \bar{Z}_{12} + 5\bar{Z}_1 + 4\bar{Z}_2 + 4\bar{Z}_4 + 4\bar{Z}_8 + 5\bar{Z}_{13} + 3\bar{Z}_5 + 2\bar{Z}_{10} + 2\bar{Z}_{20} + 2\bar{Z}_{16} \\ + 3\bar{Z}_{17}]$$

$$P_5(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_{12} + 6\bar{Z}_2 + 6\bar{Z}_4 + 4\bar{Z}_8 + 2\bar{Z}_{10} + 10\bar{Z}_{20} + 8\bar{Z}_{16}]$$

$$P_6(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_6 + 2\bar{Z}_{12} - 2\bar{Z}_2 + 2\bar{Z}_4 + 2\bar{Z}_8 - 2\bar{Z}_{10} + 2\bar{Z}_{20} + 2\bar{Z}_{16}]$$

$$P_8(x) = \frac{1}{24}[\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_3 + \bar{Z}_6 + \bar{Z}_9 + \bar{Z}_{12} + 4\bar{Z}_1 + 4\bar{Z}_2 + 4\bar{Z}_4 + 4\bar{Z}_8 + 4\bar{Z}_{13} + 2\bar{Z}_5 + 2\bar{Z}_{10} + 2\bar{Z}_{20} + 2\bar{Z}_{16} \\ + 2\bar{Z}_{17}]$$

$$P_9(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_{12} - 2\bar{Z}_2 + 2\bar{Z}_8 - 2\bar{Z}_{20} + 2\bar{Z}_{16}]$$

$$P_{10}(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 + 2\bar{Z}_6 + 2\bar{Z}_{12} + 6\bar{Z}_1 + 6\bar{Z}_2 + 4\bar{Z}_4 + 4\bar{Z}_8 + 6\bar{Z}_{13} + 2\bar{Z}_5 + 10\bar{Z}_{10} + 8\bar{Z}_{20} + 8\bar{Z}_{16} + 2\bar{Z}_{17}]$$

$$P_{12}(x) = \frac{1}{24}[\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_3 + \bar{Z}_6 - \bar{Z}_9 + \bar{Z}_{12} - \bar{Z}_1 + \bar{Z}_2 + \bar{Z}_4 + \bar{Z}_8 - \bar{Z}_{13} - \bar{Z}_5 + \bar{Z}_{10} + \bar{Z}_{20} + \bar{Z}_{16} - \bar{Z}_{17}]$$

$$P_{13}(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_{12} + 2\bar{Z}_2 + 10\bar{Z}_4 + 8\bar{Z}_8 + 6\bar{Z}_{10} + 6\bar{Z}_{20} + 4\bar{Z}_{16}]$$

$$P_{16}(x) = \frac{1}{24}[\bar{Z}_0 + \bar{Z}_3 + \bar{Z}_6 + \bar{Z}_9 + \bar{Z}_{12} + 2\bar{Z}_1 + 2\bar{Z}_2 + 2\bar{Z}_4 + 2\bar{Z}_8 + 2\bar{Z}_{13} + 4\bar{Z}_5 + 4\bar{Z}_{10} + 4\bar{Z}_{20} + 4\bar{Z}_{16} \\ + 4\bar{Z}_{17}]$$

$$P_{17}(x) = \frac{1}{24}[2\bar{Z}_0 - 2\bar{Z}_{12} + 6\bar{Z}_2 + 6\bar{Z}_4 + 4\bar{Z}_8 + 2\bar{Z}_{10} + 10\bar{Z}_{20} + 8\bar{Z}_{16}]$$

$$P_{20}(x) = \frac{1}{24}[\bar{Z}_0 - \bar{Z}_3 + \bar{Z}_6 - \bar{Z}_9 + \bar{Z}_{12} + 3\bar{Z}_1 + 2\bar{Z}_2 + 2\bar{Z}_4 + 2\bar{Z}_8 + 3\bar{Z}_{13} + 5\bar{Z}_5 + 4\bar{Z}_{10} + 4\bar{Z}_{20} + 4\bar{Z}_{16} \\ + 5\bar{Z}_{17}]$$

Minimal polynomials for $\alpha^0, \alpha^1, \alpha^2, \alpha^3, \alpha^4, \alpha^5, \alpha^6, \alpha^8, \alpha^9, \alpha^{10}, \alpha^{12}, \alpha^{13}, \alpha^{16}, \alpha^{17}$ and α^{20} are $x-1, x^2-2x+1, x^2-3, x^2-2x+1, x-3, x^2+2x-1, x^2+1, x-2, x^2-1, x^2+2, x+1, x^2+x+1, x-4, x^2-1$ and $x+2$ respectively.

The minimal codes $M_0, M_1, M_2, M_3, M_4, M_5, M_6, M_8, M_9, M_{10}, M_{12}, M_{13}, M_{16}, M_{17}$ and M_{20} of length 24 are as follows:

Code	Dim.	Min. Distance Bound	Generating Polynomial
M_0	1	24	$1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + x^8 + x^9 + x^{10} + x^{11} + x^{12} + x^{13} + x^{14} + x^{15} + x^{16} + x^{17} + x^{18} + x^{19} + x^{20} + x^{21} + x^{22} + x^{23}$
M_1	1	$8 \leq d \leq 24$	$2 + x + 6x^3 + 5x^4 + 4x^5 + 3x^6 + 2x^7 + x^8 + 6x^{10} + 5x^{11} + 4x^{12} + 3x^{13} + 2x^{14} + x^{15} + 6x^{17} + 5x^{18} + 4x^{19} + 3x^{20} + 2x^{21} + x^{22}$
M_2	1	$8 \leq d \leq 24$	$5 + 4x^2 + 6x^4 + 2x^6 + 3x^8 + x^{10} + 5x^{12} + 4x^{14} + 6x^{16} + 2x^{18} + 3x^{20} + x^{22}$
M_3	1	$6 \leq d \leq 24$	$2 + x + 6x^3 + 5x^4 + 4x^5 + 3x^6 + 2x^7 + x^8 + 6x^{10} + 5x^{11} + 4x^{12} + 3x^{13} + 2x^{14} + x^{15} + 6x^{17} + 5x^{18} + 4x^{19} + 3x^{20} + 2x^{21} + x^{22}$
M_4	1	$16 \leq d \leq 24$	$5 + 4x + 6x^2 + 2x^3 + 3x^4 + x^5 + 5x^6 + 4x^7 + 6x^8 + 2x^9 + 3x^{10} + x^{11} + 5x^{12} + 4x^{13} + 6x^{14} + 2x^{15} + 3x^{16} + x^{17} + 5x^{18} + 4x^{19} + 6x^{20} + 2x^{21} + 3x^{22} + x^{23}$
Code	Dim.	Min. Distance Bound	Generating Polynomial
M_5	1	$8 \leq d \leq 24$	$1 + 2x + 5x^2 + 5x^3 + x^4 + x^6 + 2x^7 + 5x^8 + 5x^9 + x^{10} + x^{12} + 2x^{13} + 5x^{14} + 5x^{15} + x^{16} + x^{18} + 2x^{19} + 5x^{20} + 5x^{21} + x^{22}$
M_6	1	12	$-1 + x^2 - x^4 + x^6 - x^8 + x^{10} - x^{12} + x^{14} - x^{16} + x^{18} - x^{20} + x^{22}$
M_8	1	$16 \leq d \leq 24$	$4 + 2x + x^2 + 4x^3 + 2x^4 + x^5 + 4x^6 + 2x^7 + x^8 + 4x^9 + 2x^{10} + x^{11} + 4x^{12} + 2x^{13} + x^{14} + 4x^{15} + 2x^{16} + x^{17} + 4x^{18} + 2x^{19} + x^{20} + 4x^{21} + 2x^{22} + x^{23}$
M_9	1	$6 \leq d \leq 24$	$1 + x^2 + x^4 + x^6 + x^8 + x^{10} + x^{12} + x^{14} + x^{16} + x^{18} + x^{20} + x^{22}$
M_{10}	1	$8 \leq d \leq 24$	$3 + 2x^2 + 6x^4 + 4x^6 + 5x^8 + x^{10} + 3x^{12} + 2x^{14} + 6x^{16} + 4x^{18} + 5x^{20} + x^{22}$
M_{12}	1	24	$-1 + x - x^2 + x^3 - x^4 + x^5 - x^6 + x^7 - x^8 + x^9 - x^{10} + x^{11} - x^{12} + x^{13} - x^{14} + x^{15} - x^{16} + x^{17} - x^{18} + x^{19} - x^{20} + x^{21} - x^{22} + x^{23}$
M_{13}	1	$8 \leq d \leq 24$	$-1 + x - x^3 + x^4 - x^6 + x^7 - x^9 + x^{10} - x^{12} + x^{13} - x^{15} + x^{16} - x^{18} + x^{19} - x^{21} + x^{22}$
M_{16}	1	$16 \leq d \leq 24$	$5 + 4x + x^2 + 2x^3 + 4x^4 + x^5 + 2x^6 + 4x^7 + x^8 + 2x^9 + 4x^{10} + x^{11} + 2x^{12} + 4x^{13} + x^{14} + 2x^{15} + 4x^{16} + x^{17} + 2x^{18} + 4x^{19} + x^{20} + 2x^{21} + 4x^{22} + x^{23}$
M_{17}	1	$8 \leq d \leq 24$	$1 + x^2 + x^4 + x^6 + x^8 + x^{10} + x^{12} + x^{14} + x^{16} + x^{18} + x^{20} + x^{22}$
M_{20}	1	$16 \leq d \leq 24$	$3 + 2x + 6x^2 + 4x^3 + 5x^4 + x^5 + 3x^6 + 2x^7 + 6x^8 + 4x^9 + 5x^{10} + x^{11} + 3x^{12} + 2x^{13} + 6x^{14} + 4x^{15} + 5x^{16} + x^{17} + 3x^{18} + 2x^{19} + 6x^{20} + 4x^{21} + 5x^{22} + x^{23}$

References

- [1] A. Sahni, P.T. Sehgal, Minimal Cyclic Codes of Length p^nq , Finite Fields Appl, 18(2012), 1017 – 1036.
- [2] F. Li, Q. Yue, C. Li, Irreducible Cyclic codes of length $4p^n$ and $8p^n$, Finite Fields Appl., 34(2015), 208 – 234.
- [3] G.K. Bakshi, M. Raka, Minimal Cyclic Codes of Length p^nq , Finite Fields Appl., 9(2003), 432 – 448.
- [4] J. Singh, S.K. Arora, Minimal Cyclic Codes of Length $8p^n$ over $GF(q)$, where q is prime power of the form $8k + 5$, J.Appl. Math. Comput, 48(2015), 55 – 69.
- [5] J. Singh, S.K. Arora, S. Chawla, Some Cyclic Codes of Length $8p^n$, International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, 116(1)(2017), 217 – 241.

- [6] J. Singh, S. Singh, Primitive Idempotents in FC_{8p^n} and Corresponding Codes, International Journal of Applied Engineering and Research, 14(1)(2019), 149 – 163.
- [7] J. Singh, S. Singh, Some Cyclic Codes of Length $8p^n$ over $GF(q)$, where order of q modulo $8p^n$ is $\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}$, J. Math. Comput. Science, 9(6)(2019) 654 – 677.
- [8] M. Pruthi, S.K. Arora, Minimal codes of prime power length, Finite Field Appl, 3(1997), 99 – 113.
- [9] S. Batra, S.K. Arora, Minimal Quadratic Cyclic Codes of Length p^n (p odd prime), Korean J. Comput. Appl. Math., 8(2001), 531 – 547.
- [10] S. Batra, S.K. Arora, Some Cyclic Codes of Length $2p^n$, Des. Codes Cryptogr., 61(2011), 41 – 69.
- [11] S.K. Arora, M. Pruthi, Minimal cyclic codes of length $2p^n$, Finite Field Appl. 5(1999), 177 – 187.
- [12] S.K. Arora, S. Batra, S.D. Cohen, M. Pruthi, The Primitive Idempotents of a Cyclic Group Algebra, Southeast Asian Bulletin of Mathematics, 26(2002), 549 – 557.
- [13] V. Pless, Introduction of the theory of Error Correcting Codes, Wiley, New York, 1981.